

COVINFORM

CORONAVIRUS VULNERABILITIES AND INFORMATION DYNAMICS RESEARCH AND MODELLING

D8.6 Guidelines and recommendations for communication and combating misinformation summary report

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Deliverable

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Executive Summary

The COVINFORM project examined how vulnerability is defined and addressed in response to the COVID-19 outbreak. The project drew upon complex adaptive system and intersectional approaches to offer a multilevel and interdisciplinary critique of COVID-19 responses on the levels of government, public health, community, information & communications, as well as resident perspective, and how these responses may exacerbate vulnerability and marginalisation. The current deliverable D8.6 give a summary of the outputs produced in WP7 “Inclusive COVID-19 communication for behaviour change and addressing misinformation” in the form of deliverables, white papers, policy briefs, lessons learnt, and other public outputs shared on the project website. It draws on the work conducted in WP7 that analysed COVID-19’s impact and response from a crisis communication perspective, with a specific focus on vulnerability.

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1. Introduction

The COVINFORM project examined how vulnerability is defined and addressed in response to the COVID-19 outbreak. The project drew upon complex adaptive system and intersectional approaches to offer a multilevel and interdisciplinary critique of COVID-19 responses on the levels of government, public health, community, information & communications, as well as resident perspective, and how these responses may exacerbate vulnerability and marginalisation.

Deliverable D8.6 presents a summary of the outcomes and insights of WP7, focusing on the deliverables and the outputs which provide guidance and recommendations on how to improve and effectively conduct crisis communication. The outputs provide a critical review and a cross-country analysis of existing data, as well as of original empirical data, including interviews with experts, interviews with residents, and case studies, conducted in the ten countries. The different outputs presented in this deliverable provide cross-country analysis and synthesis of the main findings, formulate lessons learnt and recommendations, as well as provide scientific findings. In addition to the deliverables of WP7, this summary reports also includes public outputs produced for WP8, published on the website of the project, like policy briefs, white papers, fact sheets, policy reports, country reports, bi-monthly reports, blog posts, videos, and podcast episodes, as well as scientific publications.

The Methodology for each output is already summarized in D8.3, and it is available in each separate output, therefore we do not reiterate it here. Some of the outputs are relevant for several of the work packages, and are hence presented multiple times across D8.3 to 8.6. In this deliverable we only highlight those aspects and sections that pertain key information on communication and fighting misinformation.

The deliverable provides a table with all the outputs containing analysis, guidance and recommendations on questions of crisis communication and combating misinformation, with dates of publication and authors. The first Chapter provides a short summary of deliverables D7.1 through D7.8. Chapter 2 presents the public outputs produced as part of WP8 and includes a summary of each output. It is divided in subchapters by type of publication. In the Conclusion, the main findings and recommendations are summarized.

Table 1. Overview of the deliverables on public health written in the context of WP5¹

Number	Date	Title	Topics covered	Authors
DELIVERABLES				
D7.1	30 Apr 2021	Baseline report: Communication and information	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • synthetic description of communication strategies • main learnings, best practices and successful communications approaches in each country • indicators to evaluate communication efficiency 	Dalila Antunes, Cláudia Rodrigues, José Manuel Palma-Oliveira, Bernardo Mendonça (FS)
D7.2	31 May 2021	Research design: Communication and information	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Proposed research design and methods • Majorly qualitative, quantitative where needed 	Niamh Aspell, Su Anson (Trilateral) Diotima Bertel, Viktoria Adler (SYNYO)
D7.3	30 Dec 2021	Analysis: Communication and information	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Analysis of communication practices, such as public health campaigns or memes • Assessment of the impact of COVID-19 communication • Good and bad practices, digital communication and exclusion, disinformation, representation and justice in media 	Viktoria Adler, Diotima Bertel (SYNYO) Marina Ghersetti, Bengt Johannsson (UGOT) Danka Foitik-Schmidt (AUTRC) Niamh Aspell, Giuseppe Forino (TRI) Dasha Ilic (MDI)
D7.4	30 Apr 2022	Synthesis and lessons learnt on communication, information and misinformation	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Multi-channel communication • Risk communication • Addressing vulnerabilities 	Viktoria Adler, Diotima Bertel (SYNYO) Su Anson (TRI)
D7.5	31 Jan 2023	Baseline report: Communication and information – Update M26	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Communication environment • Inclusion of vulnerable populations • Successful strategies 	Madalena Ricoca-Peixoto, Patrick Love (FS)
D7.6	30 Mar 2023	Research design: Communication and information – updated M29	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • update of the research design and methods • expert interviews with communication Experts 	Zainab Mehdi (TRI)
D7.7	30 Aug 2023	Analysis: Communication and information update M34	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • assessment of specific communication strategies (formats of communication, reactions of the public) • evaluation of good and bad practices 	Neda Deneva, Vanessa Götz, Viktoria Adler (SYNYO)
D7.8	27 Sep 2023	Synthesis and lessons learnt on communication, information and misinformation - update M35	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Existing vulnerabilities • Information communication • Inclusion of vulnerable populations 	Vanessa Götz, Neda Deneva (SYNYO)

¹ Public deliverables can be consulted on the project website: <https://www.covinform.eu/project-outputs/>

WP8 OUTPUTS				
White Paper	2021	Inclusive communication in times of crisis:	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Crisis communication recommendations • Barriers and possibilities of their implementation 	Su Anson, Diotima Bertel, G Havâneanu, L. Peterson
Fact Sheet	August 2023	Pandemic communication: How can we reach the most vulnerable?	Versions in English and in German <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • 5 Ts of successful communication 	Austrian Red Cross
Fact Sheet	Oct 2023	Effective and inclusive crisis communication during the COVID-19 pandemic: lessons learnt	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Recommendations for inclusive communication • Regarding the crisis communication plan, communication principles and vulnerable groups 	Neda Deneva, Vanessa Götz (SYNYO)
			•	
Policy Brief 2	Oct 2023	Addressing Vulnerability and Promoting Resilience in Social-Ecological Systems: A case study comparative analysis of the COVID-19 Pandemic throughout Europe	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Effective risk communication • Inclusive communication • Clear responsibility distribution • Multiple communication channels 	Beatriz Rosa, Benjamin Trump, José Palma-Oliveira, Igor Linkov (FS)
Policy Brief 6	Oct 2023	The impact of COVID-19 on marginalized groups in Greece	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • communication with minority groups • lack of social representation in the Roma community 	Ioannis Bagkatzounis, Ioannis Konstantopoulos, Anna Tsekoura (KEMEA)
Country report 1	July 2021	Public health response in Greece during the COVID-19 pandemic	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Analysis of Greek COVID-19 communication • Analysis over time and how crisis communication was altered 	Anna Tsekoura, Marva Arabatzi (Center for Security Studies)
Country report 2	July 2021	Governmental responses in Wales during the COVID-19 pandemic	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Analysis of Welsh COVID-19 communication campaigns • Confusion among citizens due to separate Welsh and English information 	Stéphanie Barillé, Sergei Shubin, Louise Condon & Diana Beljaars (Swansea University)
Country report 3	July 2021	Communication strategies during the COVID-19 pandemic: Wales in focus	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • risk and pandemic preparedness • understanding and responding to the emergency • best practices and guidelines on effectiveness of crisis communication 	Stéphanie Barillé, Sergei Shubin, Louise Condon & Diana Beljaars (Swansea University)
Country report 4	15 Sep 2022	Pandemic Experiences of Minority Ethnic Groups in Swansea, Neath, and Port Talbot	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Analysis of the communication and information sources for healthcare 	Diana Beljaars, Sergei Shubin (Swansea University)

Country report 5	July 2023	Crisis communication during the COVID-19 pandemic in Wales	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Evaluation of good and bad practices of the crisis communication in Wales 	Diana Beljaars, Sergei Shubin (Swansea University)
Bi-monthly report 1	Jan 2022	Viruses of the mind. Coping and joking about COVID-19.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • explorative analysis of memes • coping with the pandemic • means of communication 	Viktoria Adler & Diotima Bertel (SYNYO)
Bi-monthly report 2	July 2023	“COVID-19 communication Practices, Lessons Learned, and Recommendations”	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • analysis of good communication practices across WP2 to 8 	Su Anson, Zainab Mehdi (Trilateral)
Bi-monthly report 18	Oct 2023	How to build and how to lose trust. Lessons learned and resident perspectives on Crisis communication during COVID-19	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Analysis of resident interviews • (Mis-)Trust of residents in government, media and science over time 	Viktoria Adler, Rojin Bagheri, Vanessa Götz (SYNYO)
Blogpost 1	21 Dec 2020	Understanding vulnerability through dialogue: two-way dialogue and inclusivity in COVID-19 communication	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • considering vulnerabilities in crisis communication • implementing an inclusive and dialogue-based communication 	Peter Wieltchnig & Su Anson (Trilateral)
Blogpost 2	20 Jun 2021	Timely, transparent, targeted? Government communications during the pandemic	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • misinformation during pandemics • combatting misinformation • necessity of working with communication and crisis experts 	Patrick Love (FS)
Blogpost 3	07 July 2021	One size does not fit all – information seeking during the COVID-19 pandemic in a segregated society	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • effects of communication on ethnic minorities • challenges and possibilities regarding better tailored communication 	Bengt Johansson (University of Gothenburg)
Blogpost 4	20 Dec 2021	Antisemitic narratives find ground in COVID-19 anti-vax conspiracy theories	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • analysis of different antisemitic conspiracy theories in conjunction with COVID-19 • risks, challenges and recommendations in combatting these 	Marianna Karakoulaki (Media Diversity Institute)
Blogpost 5	22 Feb 2022	“Can we at least freak out?” Memes and COVID-19	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • analysis of memes in conjunction with COVID-19 • memes as a coping mechanism, utilizing irony and humour 	Beatrice Beghi (Sapienza University of Rome)
Blogpost 6	15 Dec 2022	Where did the UK go wrong in preparing for the COVID-19 pandemic, and how have preparedness failings tainted public trust among the UK population?	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Criticism of the UKs approach toward COVID-19 	Zainab Mehdi (Trilateral)
Blogpost 7	23 Jan 2023	“Bridging the gap”: The importance of	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • launch of the vaccination guide project in Gothenburg 	Julia Ekman (UGOT)

		interpersonal risk and crisis communication	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> to increase vaccination rates among ethnic minority communities 	
Blogpost 8	17 Aug 2023	Delivering inclusive and accessible COVID-19 communication in Birmingham (UK)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> case study of communication in Birmingham building trust and credibility making communication inclusive and accessible 	Su Anson (Trilateral)
Podcast 1	28 Feb 2022	Communication and Public Health Campaigns	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> inclusive communication analysis of good and bad practices 	Susan Anson, Marva Arabatzi (Trilateral), Panagiotis Alefragis
Podcast 2	28 Mar 2022	Data, Interpretation & Misinformation	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> infodemic making science inclusive 	Niamh Aspel, Diotima Bertel
SCIENTIFIC PUBLICATIONS				
Publication 1	2021	Understanding vulnerability to inform two-way inclusive COVID-19 communication	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> infodemic making science inclusive 	Su Anson, Peter Wieltschnig, Mistale Taylor & Niamh Aspell
Publication 2	28 Feb 2023	Meme-ing Accountability: Visual Communication as Character Assassination of Austrian and Swedish Politicians and Government Agencies during the COVID-19 Pandemic	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> information needs of vulnerable individuals, groups and communities development of inclusive communication 	Diotima Bertel, Bengt Johansson, Viktoria Adler, Marina Ghersetti
Publication 3	2023	To Stay or not to Stay at Home? The Unintended Consequences of Public Health Advice for Older Adults in the context of Covid-19 and Urban Heat	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> public health advice older adults, loneliness and isolation from stay-at-home advice 	Z. Boni, Diotima Bertel, Viktoria Adler
Publication 4	In press	Addressing COVID-19 misinformation and inequalities through communication: Insights from COVINFORM and the WHO Regional Office for Europe	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> misinformation, disinformation and trustworthiness of information infodemic' 	Su Anson & Viktoria Adler

1 Deliverables

D7.1 Baseline report: Communication and information

Authors: Dalila Antunes, Cláudia Rodrigues, José Manuel Palma-Oliveira, Bernardo Mendonça (FS)

This report focuses on providing a synthetic description of COVID-19 communication strategies and practices by governments and public health authorities in 15 countries in the EU and beyond (England, Switzerland, and Wales). The report contains a description and analysis of national COVID-19 communication by different COVINFORM partners, presenting the work developed for each country. This includes, first, the review and description of communication strategies and practices across time of governments and public health authorities on a national, regional, and local level in selected communities, including strategies to influence behaviour change, and a detailed analysis of factors influencing communication practices. Second, it includes the review of research and professional analysis to national communication on COVID-19 crisis. Third, the main learnings, best practices and successful communications approaches in each country as well as relevant indicators that can be used to evaluate communication efficiency.

The report also identifies at an early stage some main lessons and best practices for effective risk communication in pandemics (beyond the current COVID-19 pandemic), which not only emerge from countries' communication analysis, but which are also supported by the secondary sources and the literature.

D7.2 Research design: Communication and information

Authors: Niamh Aspell, Su Anson (Trilateral), Diotima Bertel, Viktoria Adler (SYNYO)

This deliverable presents an overview of the proposed research design and methods that may be applied in the empirical research activities in WPs 4 to 6. Based on a summary of the baseline evidence for government communication practices in the 15 target countries in the COVINFORM project, research questions were proposed for each partner to explore when addressing the themes of WP7, communication, disinformation and misinformation. In addition, we proposed approaches and key considerations when determining sample size and recruitment activities, and ethical considerations including obtaining informed consent.

To address the overarching research questions outlined above, the primary methods for qualitative research were considered. In some case studies, the researcher may wish to include quantitative methods and these are elaborated in *D3.2 Design research activities per case study*. Information on the data analysis methods was described, including thematic analysis and grounded theory.

This report is the first iteration of the Research Design: Communication and information deliverable, it will be continuously reviewed and updated to reflect any changes in the case study research approaches.

D7.3 Analysis: Communication and information

Authors: Viktoria Adler, Diotima Bertel (SYNYO), Marina Ghersetti, Bengt Johannsson (UGOT), Danka Foitik-Schmidt (AUTRC), Niamh Aspell, Giuseppe Forino (TRI), Dasha Ilic (MDI)

This deliverable assesses and critiques COVID-19 communication practices on key dimensions of impact. It contains seven research chapters, each focusing on a specific aspect of COVID-19 communication. The first two chapters analyse visual data of COVID-19 public health campaigns and

COVID-19 memes using a content analysis. In more detail, the first chapter engages with government communication (strategies) and the second with a particular form of communication by residents, namely memes. The following five chapters focus on government communication and use *D7.1. Baseline report: Communication and information* as a base for analysing dimensions of impact of COVID-19 communication. These dimensions are: 1.) Good and bad practices in COVID-19 communication strategies, 2.) Communication to influence behaviour change, 3.) Digital communication and exclusion, 4.) Fighting malinformation, disinformation and misinformation, 5.) Representation and justice in the media.

D7.4 Synthesis and lessons learnt on communication, information and misinformation

Authors: Viktoria Adler, Diotima Bertel (SYNYO), Su Anson (TRI)

This deliverable presents the main conclusions from the analysis in D7.3. The main finding is that countries adopted a multi-channel communication strategy during the pandemic. They primarily relied on one-way and top-down channels like press conferences, websites, and mass media. Social media and hotlines allowed for two-way communication. Many countries ran awareness campaigns targeting the general public or specific groups, sometimes involving NGOs to bridge communication gaps. NGOs also advocated for their clients' needs. However, while efforts were made for accessible and inclusive communication, there were gaps in dialogue and community engagement.

In the realm of risk communication, countries often used negative emotions, particularly fear, to convey worst-case scenarios. They also utilized positive emotions and messages of solidarity to reduce anxiety and encourage action. Clear messages and slogans with distinct goals were prevalent, but their presentation as recommendations or regulations varied. Furthermore, we identified barriers to effective risk communication, including inconsistent and conflicting messages that eroded trust. Building and maintaining trust was recognized as crucial, with some countries employing public health institutes and dedicated spokespersons as trusted sources.

Lastly, official risk communication primarily targeted the general public, yet there were efforts to address vulnerabilities and communication barriers, such as language, culture, digital accessibility, and information overload. Measures like daily or weekly press conferences and hotlines helped overcome these issues, and most countries provided information in easy-to-understand language. Ensuring messages are understandable for target audiences was a key recommendation. Centralizing communication to maintain message consistency and unity was observed in all countries, enhancing message clarity and comprehension.

D7.5 Baseline report: Communication and information – Update M26

Authors: Madalena Ricoca-Peixoto, Patrick Love (FS)

The following baseline report update sheds further light on how the COVID-19 pandemic created a challenging communication environment. Countries responded differently due to their communication infrastructure, social norms, and political context. Governments were the primary information sources, using websites, hotlines, and more. Some countries involved non-government organizations. Communication shifted from general COVID-19 information to the vaccine, lacking a formal strategy. The pandemic underscored the need for targeted and inclusive communication, emphasizing the inclusion of vulnerable populations and regional authorities. The absence of comprehensive

evaluations in some countries highlights the need for a communication component in future health crisis preparedness plans. Political landscapes and social norms influenced communication. Some countries faced political pressure and systematic evaluation, while others focused on personal responsibility, affecting trust in government communication.

We could identify several successful strategies, such as clear language, credible figures, and social media for outbreaks. Additionally, the pandemic stressed the importance of effective, targeted communication strategies in crisis management. In conclusion, there's a need for comprehensive strategy evaluations and a communication component in future health crisis preparedness plans.

D7.6 Research design: Communication and information – updated M29

Authors: Zainab Mehdi (TRI)

This report presents an update of the research design and methods that have been applied in the empirical research and case study research relating to WP7, Information and Communication. To address the overarching research questions, the consortium engaged in numerous discussions to tailor research guides for those involved in practicing communication related to COVID-19. The study participants include communication experts, i.e. journalists and government communicators. Consortium partners provided feedback on the challenges faced during recruitment, the semi-structured interviews and also valued insights regarding the conduct of the interviews. The findings from the expert interviews will be presented in D7.7, Analysis: Communication and information due in M34 (June 2023), following the same framework analysis as previously described in D3.2, Design research activities per case study'. This will be accompanied by resulting short country reports from each target country involved. Following this, the breath of evidence collated under WP7 will be synthesised and presented with clear recommendations to policy makers in respect to communication practices during crisis situations. This will be reported in D7.8, Synthesis and lessons learnt on communication, information and misinformation – update M35 (July 2023).

D7.7 Analysis: Communication and information update M34

Authors: Neda Deneva, Vanessa Götz, Viktoria Adler (SYNYO)

This deliverable presents an analysis of COVID-19 crisis management from the perspective of WP7: communication and information. The report focuses on specific communication strategies, formats of communication, reactions of the public, and the way different vulnerable groups were addressed and acknowledged in planning and implementing crisis communication. It is based on ten country report, which provide an overview of how the pandemic was managed in terms of communication management, including changes over time and lessons learned. This report contains key findings in the terms of good practices, as well as bad practices, for communicating with vulnerable groups during the COVID-19 pandemic, communication strategies in regard to their effectiveness such as to educate and persuade the public on the virus, initiatives to fight mal- and disinformation and lastly, which barriers and possibilities existed to address vulnerable groups and include them in crisis communication.

D7.8 Synthesis and lessons learnt on communication, information and misinformation - update M35

Authors: Vanessa Götz, Neda Deneva (SYNYO)

The main finding of this deliverable is the need to emphasize the contextuality and complexity of vulnerability and the necessity of tailoring crisis communication. As many countries lacked a comprehensive understanding of potential vulnerabilities in their crisis plans, this resulted in a delayed inclusion of certain groups. While most countries had initially adopted a centralized, one-size-fits-all communication approach, they later shifted to inclusive channels, expert committees, and adaptive content. In addition, response plans often fell short for a crisis of this scale and duration, relying on existing government structures. Redirecting the focus towards vulnerabilities, we found that while research on vulnerabilities exists it needs to be used to inform policy-making and be included in contingency plans for future crises. Crisis management should involve various actors, incorporate feedback, and undergo continuous evaluation. The analysis highlighted how the pandemic exacerbated existing vulnerabilities, necessitating a holistic definition in national contingency plans to reach all segments of the population and adapt communication strategies. Some governments have taken inclusive approaches, emphasizing flexibility in future planning.

2 2. WP8 outputs

2.1 White papers, policy briefs, fact sheets etc.

2.1.1 White paper

Inclusive communication in times of crisis: lessons learned and recommendations from COVID-19 and other CBRNe incidents based on recent COVINFORM & PROACTIVE findings

Authors: Su Anson, Diotima Bertel, Grigore Havârneanu & Laura Petersen

This white paper discusses the principles and practices of inclusive communication in times of crisis. The recommendations are (1) to provide an accessible and inclusive communication, for example by utilizing specific communication channels for certain groups, (2) to implement actionable communication, e.g., to give clear advice on how to behave instead of instigating fear, (3) to ensure information is trusted, credible and lastly (4) to provide relevant information in a timely manner.

However, many of these crisis communication recommendations are not new and are promoted internationally (e.g., WHO Strategic Communications Framework for Effective Communications). Past research on crisis situations already highlighted some of these critical points in various contexts. The COVID-19 pandemic revealed how many of these principles are still ignored at a wide scale, and therefore EU policymakers, Member States and Associated Countries should benefit from the momentum of the COVID-19 crisis to make sure these recommendations are adequately applied going forward.

2.1.2 Policy briefs

Addressing Vulnerability and Promoting Resilience in Social-Ecological Systems: A case study comparative analysis of the COVID-19 Pandemic throughout Europe

Authors: Beatriz Rosa, Benjamin Trump, José Palma-Oliveira, Igor Linkov (FS)

This policy brief discusses vulnerability and resilience more broadly. It addresses communication by emphasizing the importance of effective risk communication, particularly in a crisis context. One main finding is that communication structures had been fragmented and information had been contradictory. Especially, as COVID-19 had been unprecedented this had increased uncertainty. Therefore, relations between institutional bodies must have clear leadership structures. For instance, this could be achieved by establishing a single contact point for information exchange to avoid multiple and uncoordinated communication channels. Trust must be built by communicating transparently, acknowledging uncertainties and embracing inclusive participation – by making information dissemination a dialogue rather than a monologue.

Moreover, to address this challenge, it is necessary to prioritize risk communication. Hence, communication should focus on reinforcing literacy, scientific understanding, and critical thinking during normal times. During crises, the emphasis should shift to providing clear, actionable guidance to promote self-reliance and effective responses. As a one-size-fits-all approach won't work, communication strategies should be tailored to specific target populations. Understanding the diverse behaviours and needs of different groups is therefore vital, and engaging with communities to gain insights into their experiences is necessary to create effective communication.

The impact of COVID-19 on marginalized groups in Greece

Authors: Ioannis Bagkatzounis, Ioannis Konstantopoulos, Anna Tsekoura (KEMEA)

Parts of this policy brief discuss questions of communication. One main finding regards the lack of social representation of the Roma community. Communication should not be a monotonous top-down process but interactive, crisis communication should not be based on fear. Another aspect touches upon information acquisition dependent on age: younger people tend to use the internet more compared to the older populations within their communities who would often rely solely on TV as a source of information. Another finding suggests that minority group members consider communication campaigns from authorities to be insufficient and ineffective, since they were too generic, not targeting specific sub-sections of the social structure such as minority groups and very limited. Additionally, authorities were non-responsive to real time interaction requests and some representatives were unsure which information to convey upon requests.

2.1.3 Fact sheets

Pandemic communication: How can we reach the most vulnerable?

Authors: Austrian Red Cross

The fact sheet demonstrates the structural barriers for reaching vulnerable groups through crisis communication and provides recommendations for effective communication. Traditional one-way communication channels (press releases, mass media, conferences etc.) do not prove to be effective to reach vulnerable groups. Two-way communication channels, such as social media, hotlines, events, or webinars provide the opportunity to engage with the target audience and gain insights into their communication needs. It is structured as 5 Ts. Communication should be Trustworthy (Trust takes far longer to build than to destroy. Listen to people's concerns, doubts, and suggestions. Identify the right messenger and involve respected figures from communities), Timely (There is a need to inform quickly on the state of knowledge), Targeted (both in terms of audiences, and in terms of content), Transparent (clear messages with transparent sources and acknowledging limited data and uncertainty), Tactful (identifying what motivates people to change their behaviour, positive and supportive messages, instead of guilt and fear inducing)

Effective and inclusive crisis communication during the COVID-19 pandemic: lessons learnt

Authors: Neda Deneva & Vanessa Götz (SYNYO)

This factsheet addresses challenges that arose during the COVID-19 pandemic in conjunction with crisis communication and derives lessons learnt that can be clustered into three main domains: the structuring of the crisis communication plan, communication principles and handling of vulnerable groups. The crisis communication plan should exist prior to the pandemic outbreak, should define responsibilities and be evaluated periodically. Communication should generally be inclusive, straightforward, clear and simple – misinformation should be addressed and marked as such, however, uncertainties should be acknowledged, not covered up. Lastly, vulnerable groups must be identified accurately, so that information can be addressed at them adequately. Additionally, solidarity with vulnerable groups should be encouraged.

2.1.4 Country reports

Country reports present analysis across the themes from the different work packages. Here we present the take outs, recommendations and lessons learnt in relation to communication and misinformation.

Public health response in Greece during the COVID-19 pandemic

Authors: Anna Tsekoura, Marva Arabatzi (Center for Security Studies)

Communication in times of emergency such as the COVID-19 pandemic is crucial. In Greece, the Ministry of Health launched a COVID-19 campaign quite early in an effort to inform people about hygiene protocols, social distancing and on how to limit and delay the spread of COVID-19. However, in the course of the pandemic the focus of the communication campaigns changed, as did the communication means utilized for informing the public. Lastly, a governmental website was created to include all up-to-date measures and frequently asked questions in conjunction with the COVID-19 pandemic.

Governmental responses in Wales during the COVID-19 pandemic

Authors: Stéphanie Barillé, Sergei Shubin, Louise Condon, Diana Beljaars (Swansea University)

Most of the Welsh government communications are conveyed through various media channels such as television, paper and social media. The Welsh Government communicated through televised briefings to update the public on the situation and outlined the restrictions in place; it made use of media and social media to convey messages about social distancing and barrier gestures. Initially, the four nations forming the United Kingdom worked together to respond to the coronavirus pandemic, but soon each went their own way to manage the pandemic. Consistent, clear and timely guidelines are essential to pandemic management and its accompanying restrictions and would have helped the public to understand risk (Attwood & Hajat, 2021). Many people in the UK were unaware that rules and restrictions during the COVID-19 pandemic were different across the four British nations. Uncertainties around the applicability of policy announced by British Prime Minister Boris Johnson in the other nations could have been avoided if leaders of the devolved nations had made clearer that Downing Street information briefings did not always apply to Wales. It is generally agreed that not enough concerted efforts were made to convey this to the Welsh public.

Communication strategies during the COVID-19 pandemic: Wales in focus

Authors: Stéphanie Barillé, Sergei Shubin, Louise Condon, Diana Beljaars (Swansea University)

This country report focusses on communication strategies applied by public health stakeholders, organisations and communities before and during COVID-19 in Wales. Additionally, the risk and pandemic preparedness of Wales is taken into consideration, as well as their understanding and responding to the emergency. Groups and communities that were disproportionately affected by the pandemic are also touched upon. Lastly, the report summarizes the findings, by assessing the lessons learnt and best practices to derive from there guidelines on effectiveness of crisis communication.

Pandemic Experiences of Minority Ethnic Groups in Swansea, Neath, and Port Talbot

Authors: Diana Beljaars & Sergei Shubin (Swansea University)

One section of this report is dedicated to analysing the communication and information sources for healthcare, as communication also shapes their potential understanding and compliance with the pandemic regulations and measures. General knowledge about different health information outlets

was found to vary among the survey participants. There are some disparities along ethnic lines in knowledge and confidence of where to turn to address health concerns. However, the majority of the survey respondents in the Swansea, Neath and Port Talbot areas tended to rely on the health information sources provided as the NHS support service.

Crisis communication during the COVID-19 pandemic in Wales

Authors: Diana Beljaars & Sergei Shubin (Swansea University)

This report gives a brief overview of how the pandemic was managed in Wales in terms of crisis communication during the COVID-19 pandemic. Discussing the operationalisation of vulnerability, the report focuses on evaluating inclusive COVID-19 communication for behaviour change and addressing misinformation. It was found that the crisis management of the pandemic in Wales did not do enough to involve the different groups in Wales in a sufficiently equal manner. Furthermore, the division between English pandemic measures and those applied to Wales should have been more obvious for all the interviewees involved. On a positive note, the Welsh government did achieve addressing the pandemic safety issue for people experiencing homelessness and could rely on highly networked people working in public health and thereby ensuring effective collaboration.

Management and Responses of the Covid-19 Pandemic: Austria in focus

Authors: Neda Deneva & Vanessa Moser (SYNYO)

The country report summarizes the updated analysis on Austria provided for deliverables D4.7, D5.7., D6.7, and D7.7. Lessons learnt on Austria in relation to communication included the importance of strong leadership, collaboration between different actors, and effective crisis communication strategies. A lesson learnt in communicating with vulnerable populations in particular is that there are some groups that cannot be reached through governmental communication or via mass media. Even with posters or personalised letters it is impossible to create narratives that reach these groups. One way to address this challenge was to work with keypersons, who are active in certain spheres and work with particular target groups. Another best practice for the future, is immediately involving CSOs working with various vulnerable groups in order to reach these groups in a more effective way through their channels. For example, CSOs who work with different groups of migrants, with care workers, especially hard-to-reach groups like live-in caseworkers, with seasonal workers, with homeless people, with elderly people etc., should be involved from the start. Similar to other countries, key points include transparency and trust-building measures in place, coherent measures communicated in simple and clear terms, as well as the importance of involving civil society actors in the crisis management process.

2.2 Bi-monthly reports

2.2.1 Viruses of the mind. Coping and joking about COVID-19

Authors: Viktoria Adler & Diotima Bertel (SYNYO)

This report presents outcomes of an explorative analysis of memes conducted in the context of the COVIFORM project. Our aim was to gain an understanding of how humour was used to cope with the events of the pandemic and communicate with others, to share specific narratives, and to comment on experiences during the pandemic. Internet memes were also reflecting societal anxieties and

created a sense of togetherness across national borders to cope with uncertainty. Plus, they serve as a form of social commentary and criticism, utilizing humour to disseminate political critique.

2.2.2 “COVID-19 Communication Practices, Lessons Learned, and Recommendations”

Authors: Su Anson, Zeinab Mehdi (TRI)

The 16th bi-monthly report analysed communication practices among various actors across WP2 to 8. Certain common recommendation trends regarding communication across all the WPs were found. These include a strengthened collaboration between appropriate bodies, consistent and clear messaging, and understanding the needs of all vulnerable groups.

2.2.3 How to build and how to lose trust. Lessons learned and resident perspectives on Crisis communication during COVID-19

Authors: Viktora Adler, Rojin Bagheri, Vanessa Götz (SYNYO)

This bi-monthly report focuses on COVID-19 communication and trust with a focus on the perception of vulnerable groups. The aim is to illustrate the voices of vulnerable groups, in particular, of women of low socioeconomic background in Austria, Belgium, England, Germany, Greece, Italy, Portugal, Spain, Sweden, and Wales. We use the resident interviews to highlight lessons learned and recommendations that we identified through our desk-based research and expert interviews (see D7.8, WP7 whitepaper). The purpose of this report is to show a different side of the pandemic and highlight the experience of those who carried the disproportionate load of the pandemic consequences.

2.3 Blog posts

2.3.1 Understanding vulnerability through dialogue: two-way dialogue and inclusivity in COVID-19 communication

Authors: Peter Wieltschnig & Su Anson (Trilateral Research)

This blogpost discusses the importance of understanding vulnerability through dialogue in COVID-19 communication. It highlights the impact of existing vulnerabilities on the severity of infection rates and socio-economic impacts. It emphasizes the need to adopt an intersectional lens when developing response measures to address vulnerabilities. Furthermore, there is a strong need for two-way communication and dialogue with communities to understand their risk perceptions, behaviours, and specific needs. This shift from top-down to inclusive communication is crucial. It also emphasizes the importance of providing realistic advice that considers the capacities of different communities, rather than a one-size-fits-all approach as inadequate communication strategies can lead to stigmatization and xenophobia among marginalized community groups, making it essential to include their experiences in communication strategies. Understanding vulnerability through dialogue is vital in COVID-19 communication. Inclusive and tailored approaches are imperative to address the diverse challenges and needs arising from the pandemic.

2.3.2 Timely, transparent, targeted? Government communications during the pandemic

Author: Patrick Love (FS)

The blogpost discusses the historical presence of false and misleading information during pandemics and highlights the influence of human behaviour on disease outbreaks. It mentions the role of fear and panic in shaping responses to epidemics and the impact of human psychology on contagion dynamics. The blogpost also touches on the importance of communication strategies during the COVID-19 pandemic and the need for timely, transparent, and targeted communication. Furthermore, in order to reduce the decline in trust in institutions and governments, the use of experts in communication is important. A major challenge when communicating on pandemics such as COVID-19 is dealing with uncertainty. Nevertheless, it is necessary to address these challenges and improve communication in order to the impact of misinformation among the public.

2.3.3 One size does not fit all – information seeking during the COVID-19 pandemic in a segregated society

Author: Bengt Johansson (UGOT)

Communicating a pandemic has many challenges, not least in relation to vulnerable groups such as ethnic minorities. There is a well-known paradox in crisis and risk communication when those who are most affected are hardest to reach. In addition, minority groups tend to have low trust toward government authorities and other official sources, which reduces compliance with recommended protective measures. Hence, information seeking patterns may help to explain higher death tolls in COVID-19 in immigration dense areas in Sweden. Information gaps widens with language problems and weak identification with the majority society.

2.3.4 Antisemitic narratives find ground in COVID-19 anti-vax conspiracy theories

Author: Marianna Karakoulaki (Media Diversity Institute)

The article underscores the impact of social media in spreading these conspiracy theories – regarding the use of Holocaust comparisons or other antisemitic conspiracy theories – and the challenges faced in addressing them. Further, it was analysed how fear is utilized by those spreading a conspiracy mindset. It provides nine recommendations, including better cooperation among civil society organizations, tech companies, and lawmakers, as well as improved social media moderation, training for moderators, and strengthening collaboration among CSOs to combat online hate and misinformation.

2.3.5 “Can we at least freak out?” Memes and COVID-19

Author: Beatrice Beghi (Sapienza University of Rome)

This blog post explores how memes were used as a coping mechanism and a means to share experiences during the COVID-19 pandemic. Memes offered a way to find humour and solace in an otherwise challenging and grim situation. The post highlights the different types of memes, including those related to politicians, and acknowledges that humour can be a divisive coping strategy, as some find it disrespectful while others appreciate it as an escape from reality. The post also discusses how the pandemic has increased feelings of loneliness, fear, and depression, prompting a greater reliance on online sociality and memes as a form of distraction. The "go out of our minds" meme is featured as a reflection of people's fear of confronting their inner selves and the anxiety associated with solitude. Ultimately, the post suggests that humour and irony in memes serve as a way to address these complex emotions during the pandemic.

2.3.6 Where did the UK go wrong in preparing for the COVID-19 pandemic, and how have preparedness failings tainted public trust among the UK population?

Author: Zainab Mehdi (Trilateral Research)

The United Kingdom's response to the COVID-19 pandemic faced criticism, particularly in the realm of communication. Initially adopting a "herd immunity" approach led to confusion and mistrust. The lack of relevant pandemic exercises and failure to utilize findings from Exercise Cygnus also hampered effective communication and preparedness. The revelation of rule-breaking parties at Downing Street further eroded public trust in the government's communication and guidance. Restoring trust in COVID-19 measures and future pandemic responses requires investments in anthropological research and demonstrating accountability to address public concerns and regain confidence in government communication.

2.3.7 "Bridging the gap": The importance of interpersonal risk and crisis communication

Author: Julia Ekman (UGOT)

In the autumn of 2021, the Swedish COVID-19 vaccination roll-out was in full progress and vaccines had become available for all Swedish adults. Although there was a sufficient vaccine supply, it became increasingly evident that the vaccination rates were significantly lower among populations of foreign-born individuals living in areas with socio-economic challenges. The so-called vaccination guide project was launched in the city of Gothenburg – a network-based risk and crisis communication initiative, aiming to increase vaccination rates in ethnic minority communities. Vaccination guides refer to people working in ethnic minority communities, talking and connecting with people to inform them about COVID-19 vaccines.

2.3.8 Delivering inclusive and accessible COVID-19 communication in Birmingham (UK)

Author: Su Anson (Trilateral Research)

Birmingham City Council recognized the importance of inclusive and accessible communication during the COVID-19 pandemic, especially for vulnerable groups in their "super diverse" community. To meet this challenge, they conducted extensive research to understand the specific information needs of various communities. Their approach included online surveys, ethnographic research, and collaborations with community engagement partners to develop culturally sensitive messages. They also established a community champions program and utilized community radio and media to reach diverse groups. Building trust and credibility was prioritized through transparency, scientific evidence, and engagement with faith-based organizations. The use of community champions enabled real-world testing of COVID-19 communication and co-production of solutions to overcome language and literacy barriers. Birmingham City Council's direct and inclusive approach illustrates the significance of community engagement and two-way communication in effective crisis response.

2.4 Podcasts

2.4.1 Communication and Public Health Campaigns

Participants: Su Anson & Marva Arabatzi (Trilateral), Panagiotis Alefragis

How to make communication inclusive? And what are the good and bad practices when communicating measures and policies during the COVID-19 pandemic? The second episode of the

Beyond Number: COVID-19 and Society podcast focuses on summarising the importance of inclusive communication during a crisis such as the pandemic. Dr Susan Anson and Marva Arabatzi discuss topics such as behaviour change, misinformation, inclusive communication and many more. The special guest, Panagiotis Alefragis, the Head of Digital & 360 Advertising Director at the Newtons Laboratory, shares his first-hand experience with creating public health campaigns in Greece.

2.4.2 Data, Interpretation & Misinformation

Participants: *Niamh Aspell (Trilateral), Diotima Bertel (SYNYO)*

What is the infodemic, and how to make data science more inclusive? The third episode of Beyond Numbers: COVID-19 and Society podcast is about numbers, but not only. During the pandemic, we were confronted with an unprecedented amount of data. Daily cases, death rates or vaccination effectiveness. The experts of this episode, Diotima Bertel and Dr Niamh Aspell, discuss many topics related to data and data interpretation, such as the rise of misinformation, interdisciplinary collaboration, and surprisingly memes

2.5 Scientific publications

Understanding vulnerability to inform two-way inclusive COVID-19 communication.

Authors: Su Anson, Peter Wieltchnig, Mistale Taylor & Niamh Aspell

As a global pandemic, COVID-19 has resulted in a variety of different epidemiological, cultural, political, and socio-economic impacts. However, similar to other disasters, COVID-19 is disproportionately impacting particular groups, including vulnerable populations. In this paper, the authors examine how there is a need to understand the concept of vulnerability and the information needs of vulnerable individuals, groups and communities through an intersectional lens in order to develop inclusive communication that is accessible to different groups. Two-way communication and ongoing interaction are a necessary step in ensuring that vulnerable groups are not excluded from COVID-19 communication practices, potentially further increasing their vulnerability.

Meme-Ing Accountability: Visual Communication as Character Assassination of Austrian and Swedish Politicians and Government Agencies During the COVID-19 Pandemic

Authors: *Diotima Bertel, Bengt Johansson, Viktoria Adler, Marina Gherseti*

In the contemporary digital society, a way of contesting power and claiming public accountability is through the use and spread of political memes as a viral, multimodal (visual and text) genre of communication in the intersection between popular culture and politics. During the COVID-19 pandemic, just like in other contemporary issues, memes of success and failures in the management of the crisis went viral on social media. This chapter explores and compares how negative political memes were used in Austria and Sweden to articulate character assassination of leading politicians and other public power holders responsible for handling the pandemic. Three different dimensions of character assassination are identified which involve qualities of ethics, competence, and appearance. Four memes from each country are analysed, all collected between March 2020 and June 2021. The analysis shows that the memes commented on, criticized, and mocked leading politicians and other public officials during the ongoing crisis. Critical evaluations were often expressed in a single meme by a combination of two different dimensions of character assassination. Attacks on ethics and competence were identified, as well as on appearance and competence. However, this was not the

case on the combination of appearance and ethics. Similarities in the use of memes were found between Austria and Sweden, but also important differences: while the physical appearance of politicians and other power holders was commonly addressed in the Austrian memes, this did not occur in the Swedish ones. Instead, appearance was here addresses in a symbolic and figurative sense.

To Stay or not to Stay at Home? The Unintended Consequences of Public Health Advice for Older Adults in the context of COVID-19 and Urban Heat

Authors: Boni Z., Diotima Bertel, Viktoria Adler

Stay-at-home advice is one of the most widespread public health solutions to various health risks, including COVID-19 and heat stress. Authorities often direct this recommendation at adults above the age of 65, a group particularly vulnerable to multiple risks. While this advice aims to save lives, it also comes with various negative unintended consequences. Specifically, it increases older adults' isolation and loneliness, which negatively affects their mental and physical health, as well as their wellbeing and quality of life. The article builds on the findings from two European projects that studied, respectively, COVID-19 responses and adaptation strategies to urban heat. Based on that, it demonstrates why stay-at-home advice might be problematic for older adults and how it leads to their increased loneliness and isolation when it stops being a short-term measure and becomes a prolonged experience. Public health advice should consider the issues of temporality, sociality and inequality when re-considering the implementation of stay-at-home advice in the future. A focus on community wellbeing, instead of thinking only in terms of individual health and responsibility, might be a way forward.

Addressing COVID-19 misinformation and inequalities through communication: Insights from COVINFORM and the WHO Regional Office for Europe

Authors: Su Anson, Viktoria Adler

The COVID-19 pandemic has resulted in a variety of global social, economic and physical impacts. This includes heightening awareness of the dangers of misinformation (unintentional spread of false information), disinformation (false information purposely spread; colloquially called 'fake news'), and malinformation (information based in reality but is used to cause harm). While COVID-19 has led to the overwhelming use of social media and technology to share information on protective measures (e.g., physical distancing, wearing face masks), it has also resulted in the spread of false information. As a result, the World Health Organization (WHO) has classified COVID-19 as an 'infodemic'. The infodemic is a challenge to public health emergency response because it makes trustworthy information harder to find. Particularly at the beginning of the pandemic, in the absence of vaccination or approved treatment, effective risk communication that influenced behaviour change was the only measure to reduce the spread of the virus. Misinformation not only results in the lack of adoption of healthy protective behaviours (e.g., vaccination) but has promoted incorrect practices that increase the spread of COVID-19 and lead to poor physical and mental health. As such, the infodemic puts health and lives at risk. Misinformation does not impact everyone equally with studies highlighting differential impacts based on sociodemographic factors such as employment status, ethnicity, religion, gender, and income. The term "infodemically vulnerable" highlights the information inequalities that exist and how some people may be less able to counter misinformation resulting in them relying on unreliable sources.

3 Conclusion

WP7 discusses the critical importance of crisis communication in managing the COVID-19 pandemic and highlights key lessons learned from various countries' experiences. The COVID-19 pandemic revealed significant challenges related to crisis communication plans. Many of the countries researched in the COVINFORM project lacked adequate crisis communication strategies, which hindered their ability to respond effectively and communicate clearly during the outbreak. Sweden, as an example, was better prepared due to existing policies and a strong division of responsibilities, which reduced confusion. In contrast, countries like Germany and Wales faced issues with contradictory messages and confusion due to a lack of coordination.

Recommendations across countries include:

- Involving health experts and scientists in pandemic communication enhanced the credibility of information and public trust in government decisions. This approach also prevented politicians from exploiting the crisis for political gain.
- Cooperation with media, regional authorities, and civil society organizations was crucial to combat misinformation and reach vulnerable groups. Coordination among these entities was essential to avoid contradictory messages.
- Clear and detailed crisis communication plans that include flexible and long-term strategies are necessary. These plans should be regularly evaluated and incorporate lessons learned. Communication must be tailored to specific audiences, with a focus on making information accessible to all, including vulnerable groups.
- Transparency in decision-making, based on scientific evidence, is vital. Expert involvement at all levels and the publication of guidelines and reports increase public trust. Crisis management should involve a variety of actors, be flexible, and include feedback loops.
- A holistic understanding of vulnerability is essential in crisis communication plans, as vulnerabilities can vary depending on the context. Governments need to recognize and address different types of vulnerabilities and adapt communication strategies accordingly.
- It is necessary that research informs policy-making and ensure that vulnerabilities are considered in contingency plans.
- Crisis management should be multi-dimensional and incorporate feedback from various groups.

In conclusion, the COVID-19 pandemic emphasized the importance of crisis communication plans and their adaptability. Lessons learnt include the need for clear and coordinated communication, expert involvement, and a focus on vulnerable groups. Flexibility, ongoing evaluation, and a holistic approach to vulnerability are critical in addressing future crises effectively.